

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH "DEMOKRITOS"

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*From risk imagination to safety intervention -
Managing risks with knowledge*

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Keynote Lecture 4

A science of professional engineering practice: our next step towards a safer engineering industry.

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This keynote takes the author's 44-year career history as a civil & structural engineer as its frame. This began with hands-on work 'at the sharp end' of construction, then led to senior roles in industry and in the professional institutions. The narrative is presented, however, in terms of the author's journey of reflection and deduction about engineering as a practice, and about management and leadership in the profession.

As an engineer, the author is highly motivated towards safety in the construction phase and, being conventionally trained, naturally likes a rational basis for action. In professional practice, however, it soon became apparent that a purely explicit basis for action was insufficient. Even in areas as straightforward as conventional design and routine building work, where published rules and guidance set precedent, judgement and caution based on intuition were needed, and a wider skill-set and professional attitude. This was even more the case in the management of engineering practice. Here the management of designers and engineering practitioners relied almost entirely on evolved processes embedded in businesses' processes and attitudes.

Developing as a business leader, the author became aware of how important it is that his safety-critical profession makes clear its own needs within the broader context of engineering business leadership. Here engineering judgements are contested, as are claims for resources. In this regard, the civil & structural engineering profession has relied for too long on its industry leaders being drawn from amongst its own ranks. Where this is not the case there is less empathy, and issues such as training and development are at risk if needs are not negotiated; more critically, engineering-based safety judgements to stop production or progress must carry sway, notwithstanding other pressures. In these situations engineers are helped enormously by making a rational case for their assertions. Knowing that intuition, for instance, even feelings, are respected parts of professional practice gives engineers confidence in making their case when themselves reliant on these types of knowledge.

To an engineer educated to seek explicit explanation, this situation seemed curious. Even in the most basic examples of design and making, the role of knowledge other than the taught 'engineering sciences' was not made clear. This was even more the case in the management and leadership of engineering practice: leaders and managers were not guided to look for, nurture and trust intuition, feel and other non-explicit knowledge forms in their engineering teams. If these knowledge forms are accepted as important to engineers, then the profession, which positions itself as based on empirical science, seems to be falling short of its own standards by lacking a science of professional engineering practice. For instance, if intuition and judgement are needed, what are they, how should they be treated, developed, accessed and used, and how can we assess their reliability? A particular challenge is when the way things are done is changed, or innovated. In these cases, if we lack adequate understanding, unexpected outcomes are almost inevitable. Indeed, reviewing failures occurring in the industry, the author and peers in safety engineering groups identified this as a recurring theme.

This prompted the author to use his positions in industry and in the profession to make explicit the processes that aided safety but were unwritten, possibly not understood, some not even recognised. His roles gave him material to work on, time to reflect, safe places to test ideas, peers to work and spar with, and test-beds to make trials. Models of understanding and behaviour that the author has worked on will be presented in the keynote, covering areas of epistemology, the role of institutions, and how the processes of 'doing engineering' can be strengthened to improve safety in operations and outcomes for society.

The work is not complete. The keynote advocates that as a profession we have more to do to understand our own profession ourselves, and then, from this, to explain it to others. Engineering is now an intrinsic part of our existence on our planet. As engineers we have a vital role to play, we are in a team, our colleagues and leaders are not all engineers, and the stakes are high. The author advocates that we must be on top of our own game, and to this end need to understand ever better the way we work and how this can best contribute to the societal benefits we espouse. He hopes that the material he presents is useful to the audience, and looks forward to the discussion.

References

Brady S (2013): The 30 year failure cycle. The Structural Engineer, Institution of Structural Engineers London, May 2013 pp. 14–15.

Edmondson V et al (2017) Advancing tunnelling: recognising an engineering legacy. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers – Forensic Engineering 170(4): 191–199, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jfoen.17.00012>.

Edmondson V et al (2018): Advancing tunnelling: the Victorian engineering management legacy. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers – Forensic Engineering 171(2): 49–57, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jfoen.18.00002>.

Hewlett B (2020): Briefing: Temporary Works Forum: how history and narrative shaped a major safety initiative. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers – Forensic Engineering, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jfoen.20.00001>.

Hewlett B, Sherratt F and Edmondson V (2022): Managing designing for safety: a framework for whole-team decision making and risk control. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers – Management, Procurement and Law, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jmapl.22.00030>.

HSE (Health and Safety Executive) (1976): Final Report of the Advisory Committee on Falsework. Her Majesty's Stationery Office, London, UK. *'The Bragg Report'*.

Kurtz CF & Snowden DJ (2003): The new dynamics of strategy: Sense-making in a complex and complicated world. IBM Systems Journal Vol 42 No 3 pp462-483.